

Technical Evaluation of a Chemical Looping Combustor Fed With Biofuels And Its Integration With a Gas Turbine

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Abstract –Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) technologies are fundamental to absorb CO₂ from the atmosphere and store it underground. A way to develop such kind of technologies is that to couple a pressurized chemical looping combustor to a turbo expander. The typical configuration chosen is to have an air reactor and a fuel reactor based on coupled circulating fluidized beds. The fluidization regime in the fuel reactor is bubbling, while the fluidization regime in the air reactor is fast. To design the two reactors Aspen Plus software was used, given that the new version has a module for fluidized bed modeling. At first the oxygen carrier has been designed ex novo, given that it is a composite compound, mainly made by nickel oxide freeze granulated on alumina (Ni40Al-FG), the molecular structure has been inserted in Aspen Plus. Then based on the power of the gas turbine the mass flow of evolved fluid (in this case depleted air) is calculated using Aspen Plus. The fuel reactor is modelled inserting the reduction reactions for nickel based oxygen carrier.

1 Introduction (First level heading)

In both the Fifth Assessment and the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways reports, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) identifies Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) as a key technology to meet the goal of limiting the increase in the global temperature to less than 2°C, see [1]. BECCS is still under development, nevertheless and a big help can be given by coupling bioenergy with chemical looping combustion, see for example the recent work of Mendiara et al [2] or the work of Ryden et al [3]. Many review papers have already dealt with several aspects of chemical looping, see for example [4-9]. There is also a recent interest on pressurized chemical looping as reported in [10]. Nevertheless, work on coupling of PCLC reactors with turbo expanders is still not complete, given that there are many barriers that this process is facing and also considering the relative novelty of CLC technology. This is true especially if we consider biomass as a fuel.

In this context a Marie Curie project has been funded by the European Commission and it is managed in the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Instituto de Carboquímica (ICB) in Zaragoza, with the name of “GTCLC-NEG”, which wants to develop a Carbon Negative Technology, able to burn multiple biofuels derived from biomass (eg, pyrolysis oil, biogas and syngas) and to capture the CO₂ emissions at a very low cost. In this way there will be negative GHG emissions, due to the use of BECCS (Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage). The proposed plant is based on the coupling of a Chemical Looping Combustor to a turbo expander, as proposed in figure 1.

Figure 1: The GTCLC-NEG concept [11]

As it can be seen from Figure 1, compressed air is used to oxidize the oxygen carrier and then expanded in a turbo expander to produce electricity. In the fuel reactor biofuels (eg. biogas, biomethane, syngas, pyrolysis oils, biodiesel, bioethanol and pulverized solids biofuels) are used to reduce the oxygen carrier. The gases exiting the fuel reactor are mainly composed by CO₂ and water vapor. They can also expand into a turbo expander and provide electrical energy. After the expansion process the gases expanding from the fuel reactor can exchange energy with a Heat Recovery Steam Generator (HRSG) and then the water vapor contained in the gases can be condensed and be separated from the CO₂, which is sent to a compression section that at the end will produce liquefied CO₂. Also the gases which have expanded in the turbine at the exit of the air reactor are used to recover heat to produce steam. So two different HRSGs are needed, because we cannot mix the two flows of gases exiting the air and the fuel reactor; otherwise we will eliminate the advantage of the CLC technology, which is that to produce a pure flow of CO₂ after water condensation. The vapor produced by the two HRSGs can be sent to a steam turbine (in this case we have assumed to use 2 steam turbines, because we want to have an idea of the energy which can be produced separately at the AR reactor and at the FR reactor).

Based on what has been reported above, it is of key importance to develop methodology to design Pressurised Chemical Looping Combustion (PCLC) plants which have to be coupled to gas turbines. If we consider the classical steps which have been followed in the design of chemical looping combustion plants, we can think at the methodology reported in [12]. In this it is stated that the advantages of coupling two fluidized beds to build a CLC combustor are the following:

1. it can grant effective solid material circulation between the two reactors;
2. through an accurate management of the solids inventory in both the reactor it can be achieved a satisfactory conversion of the gases fed to the air and to the fuel reactor;
3. this is very probably the only configuration which minimizes gas leakages through the presence of a loop seal.

In the specific case of this work, the methodology reported in [12] is adapted to take into account the final use of the combustor (i.e. producing power when coupled to a gas turbine). As it can be seen from figure 2 the design of the CLC plant starts by choosing the power output of the combustor, based on this the fuel and air mass flows are determined and so the air to fuel ratio. The solids circulation is determined then from the solid heat and mass balance, but it is the heat balance which is the most important aspect to consider. The velocities which are typical of the riser (which consists of the last part of the air reactor) are usually 4-10 times the terminal velocity. Where with terminal velocity we indicate the lowest velocity at which the particles start to move with the gas and so the entrainment process begins [13]. For the fuel reactor instead usually velocities of about 0.7 times the terminal velocity or 2 times the minimum fluidization velocity are taken into account. Another important aspect is related to the pressure drop, this depends essentially by the height of the bed which also it is linked with the particle residence time. Given that the reduction reaction is usually less reactive than the oxidation reaction usually the height of the fuel reactor bed is higher than that of the air reactor bed. In the specific case of [12] it is assumed that the freeboard of the fuel reactor has to be twice high than the dense bed. On the other hand, it is highly advisable to have similar pressure drops in the air reactor and in the fuel reactor, because otherwise this could result in a disequilibrium on the loop seal.

Based on this considerations we have introduced a revised procedure to design pressurized chemical looping combustors which have to be coupled to turbo expanders in power plants. In this case the first difference we can note is that the air mass flow and the fuel mass flow are determined by the power that it will be produced by the turbo expander connected to the air reactor. We assume at least for now the power produced at the outlet of the air reactor because this represents the great part of the total power production, given that the mass flow of air from the air reactor is much higher than that of CO₂ and water vapor exiting the fuel reactor and also given that the heat which can be recovered from the expanded gases will be anyway lower than that produced from the turbo expander. In this case the revised design procedure for the whole plant is that shown in figure 2. In this sense this work can be considered a continuation of what was done already by NTNU, see [14].

The methodology proposed in figure 2 is based on the following steps:

- the first step is to select the capacity of the desired turbine, based also on the biomass available in the territory where the project is developed;
 - the second is to take into consideration the desired specifications of the turbine (like the turbine inlet temperature and the compression ratio);
 - the third is to identify the mass flow of air;
 - the fourth is to use a balance of energy applied to the fuel and air reactor to optimize the quantity of excess air reducing the use of fuel and granting high temperatures at the inlet of the turbine,
 - the fifth is to identify in a recursive way the optimal quantity of fuel;
 - the sixth is to calculate the oxygen carrier circulation rate;
 - the seventh is to calculate the oxygen carrier inventory;
 - the eighth is to calculate detailed mass and energy balances of the plant and so its efficiency.
- In this paper, after having analyzed the air reactor in another work, we propose:
- a summary of the characteristics of the air reactor
 - a more detailed analysis of the characteristics of the fuel reactor;
 - a comparison of the two.

The work has been realized using Aspen V11 software.

Figure 2: Design procedure for a power plant using a pressurized chemical looping combustor coupled with a turbo expander

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Air Mass flow calculation

The first design of the power plant is based on the assumption that the power of the turbo expander is of 12 MWe. To produce this power it is calculated by the Aspen plus model that about 135 t/h of air is need to be compressed and then expanded in the gas turbine. Now we have to consider that the excess air which expands in the gas turbine has to be the highest as possible, see for example what it is reported in [14] and also in [15], in which it is proposed an excess air ratio which is up to 3.7. If the excess air is high the fuel consumption to obtain the same effect will be low and so the efficiency of the plant will be maximized.

If we chose an excess air of 3, we obtain that based on stoichiometric calculation the stoichiometric air-to-fuel ratio for a syngas composed of 50v% of CO and 50v% of H₂ is: 4.6 kg air/kg syngas. This means that if we have a flow of 135 t/h air, the flow of methane will be equal to 9.7 t/h. The mass of fuel has been calculated according to equation 1.

$$\dot{m}_F = \frac{\dot{m}_{AIR}}{\text{alfa}} / ATFR \quad (1)$$

Where alfa is the excess air and ATFR is the Air To Fuel Ratio.

2.2 The Aspen Plus Model

The Aspen Plus model is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3 Aspen Plus project of the air reactor (AR) and fuel reactor (FR).

As it can be seen from Fig. 3, in the proposed plant compressed air is used to oxidize the oxygen carrier and then it is expanded in a turbo expander to produce power. In the fuel reactor biofuels are used to reduce the oxygen carrier. The gases exiting the fuel reactor are mainly composed by CO₂ and water vapor. They can also expand into a turbo expander and provide further electricity. After the expansion process the gases can exchange their residual energy with a Heat Recovery Steam Generator (HRSG) and then the water vapor contained in the gases exiting the fuel reactor can be condensed and be separated from the CO₂. In the same way also the gases which have expanded in the turbine at the exit of the air reactor are used to recover heat to produce steam. So, two different HRSGs are needed, because we cannot mix the two flows of gases exiting the air and the fuel reactor. The vapor produced by the two HRSGs can be sent to a team turbine (in this case we have assumed to use 2 steam turbines, because we want to have an idea of the energy, which can be produced separately at the AR reactor and the FR reactor).

2.3 Solids circulation rate in the air reactor

The circulation rate is calculated mainly based on a mass balance applied to the fuel reactor and depends on the conversion variation of the oxygen carrier obtained in the fuel and air reactor. Given that the flow of syngas is already known, we can calculate the circulation rate, according to equations 2 and 3.

$$\dot{m}_{\text{ox}} = b_r M_{\text{NiO}} F_f \Delta X_f / (x_{\text{NiO}} \Delta X_s) \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{m} = \dot{m}_{\text{ox}} (1 + R_0 x_{\text{NiO}} (X_{S,o} - 1)) \quad (3)$$

Where:

- b_r is the stoichiometric factor in the reduction reactions, expressed in mol of solid reacting per mol of fuel gas.
- M is the molecular weight of the material, expressed in g per mole;
- F_f is the molar flow of the fuel gas, expressed in moles/s;
- ΔX_f is the conversion rate of the fuel gas, which is assumed to be equal to 1;
- x_{NiO} is the mass fraction of NiO in the fully oxidized sample; this is indicated in many cases in the name of the catalyst, for example if we take into consideration Ni40Al-FG: the number 40 means 40% in mass of nickel metal is contained. This oxygen carrier has been tested in pressurized conditions at the Instituto de Carboquímica, see [16];
- ΔX_s represents the conversion of the solids. In fact not all the solids which are circulating in the reactor are fully converted, we can assume that 0.3 of the solids is converted, as reported for example in: [17].
- another key parameter of the oxygen carrier, after the mass fraction of metal, is the R_0 , which is the oxygen transport capacity of the active metal oxide (for active metal oxide we indicate

the part of the metal oxide which has not reacted with the support and so can actively behave as an oxygen carrier). These two data: mass fraction of metal oxide and oxygen transport capacity are indicated in table 1 for Ni40Al-FG and are key parameters also for the design of the fuel and air reactor. R0 can be calculated according to equation 6, as reported in [18].

- XS,o is the solids conversion in the oxidation reaction.

The main characteristics of the oxygen carrier used are shown in table 1.

The oxygen carrier is derived from a freeze granulation preparation process, performed at Chalmers University, according to what reported in [19]. Based on equations 2 and 3 the final calculation of the circulation rate results to be equal to 111 kg/s, which is not excessive for a power plant producing 12 MWe and considering also other values reported in literature, see [17].

Table 1: Ni40Al-FG Oxygen carrier characteristics [16]

Active NiO content	40	wt%
Oxygen transport capacity, R0	0.084	-
Particle size	0.2	(μm)
Porosity	0.36	%
Specific surface area (BET)	0.8	m ² /g
Solid density	5380	kg/m ³

On the components section, when selecting an oxygen carrier to be inserted as a component the ID should be introduced in form of the chemical formula of the compound (eg. Al₂O₃-NiO); if this identity is not recognized as a compound contained in the database linked with Aspen Plus software, the compound has to be user defined, specifying the following parameters:

- component ID and Alias are identified as the compound chemical formula;
- compound state (in the case of the oxygen carrier we consider solid state);
- Molecular weight;
- Normal boiling point;
- Solid enthalpy of formation;
- Solid Gibbs energy of formation;
- Molar volume data (here also the density of the solid can be inserted);
- Vapor pressure data;
- Extended Antoine vapor pressure coefficients;
- Solid heat capacity data;
- Solid heat capacity polynomial coefficient.

The final data after they have been inserted in the software are proposed in the following table 3.

Dealing with the solid heat capacity coefficient, the solid molar volume, these are estimated based on the polynomial of alumina (Al₂O₃) and Nickel (Ni and NiO), which are assumed to be inserted separately, given that it is assumed that there is no chemical linkage between the two.

Another step is represented by the necessity to model the Particle Size Distribution inside the air reactor a PSD mesh is used and it can be seen in table 3, as calculated with Aspen Plus V11. To realize the mesh a distribution function is built. This is based on the GGS (Gates–Gaudin–Schuhmann) approach, see [20]. The dispersion parameter is set to 1.5 and the maximum diameter is set to 0.4 mm. The minimum value of the distribution is set to be 0.1 mm.

Table 2: PSD inside the air reactor calculated with ASPEN Plus V11

Interval	Lower limit	Upper limit (μm)	Weight fraction (μm)	Cumulative weight fraction
1	100	130	0,185279	0,185279
2	130	160	0,0677037	0,252982
3	160	190	0,0743889	0,327371
4	190	220	0,0805198	0,407891
5	220	250	0,086215	0,494106
6	250	280	0,0915561	0,585662
7	280	310	0,0966021	0,682264
8	310	340	0,101397	0,783661
9	340	370	0,105975	0,889637
10	370	400	0,110363	1

The image of the PSD distribution is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: PSD distribution of Ni particles

By the point of view of the reactions, equations 1 and 2 indicate reduction of carbon monoxide and hydrogen respectively (assuming that syngas is used as a fuel). Reaction indicates oxidation.

When nickel is used also water gas shift reactions has to be taken into account. The kinetic of these reactions is proposed in [16].

2.4 Solids Inventory calculation for the Chemical Looping Combustion plant

A clear way to identify the inventory in the air reactor is to refer to data on the kinetics of the oxidation reaction in pressurized conditions, see [21-23]. The final inventory needed in the air reactor can be calculated referring to the equation which has been reported in [16] and also the work published previously at the Instituto de Carboquímica in Zaragoza [17, 24].

In [17] for example it is clearly shown how to calculate the solids inventory for both: the air reactor and the fuel reactor (moc):

$$\mathbf{m}_{\text{OC}} = \mathbf{y}_g \Delta \mathbf{X}_g \frac{2d\mathbf{M}_O}{R_0} \frac{\bar{\tau}_r}{\Phi_{\text{FR}}} \quad (7)$$

Equation 4 is for the determination of the solids inventory of the fuel reactor. For the determination of the inventory of the oxygen carrier in the air reactor we simply substitute the $\bar{\tau}_r$ and the Φ_{FR} with $\bar{\tau}_o$ and Φ_{AR} . Dealing with the other parameters, y_g can be considered equal to 1, $\Delta \mathbf{X}_g$ is equal to 0.999. While R_0 is a parameter which is typical of the oxygen carrier, d and M_o are typical of the reaction. In fact, d is the stoichiometric factor in the fuel combustion reaction with oxygen (expressed in mol O₂ per mol of fuel). M_o is the molar mass of oxygen (so it is 16). The expression: $\frac{2d\mathbf{M}_O}{R_0}$ represents the characteristic circulation rate (also the enthalpy of reaction can be included in the expression at the denominator if we want to express the characteristic circulation rate based on the MW of primary energy of the reactor), also identified with the symbol: $\dot{\mathbf{m}}_c$. The parameter Φ_{FR} is the characteristic reactivity, which depends by the solid conversion at the inlet, $X_{r,\text{in}}$, and the conversion variation ΔX_r , see [24]. Applying the above determined equations we calculated a final inventory for the air reactor of about: 2720 kg. It has also to be considered that, as reported in [25], the real inventory needed can be from 2 to 10 times higher than the theoretical one, which we have calculated before. So we foresee that the real inventory for the air reactor would be about 10,880 kg (about four times the theoretical one).

2.5 Transport Disengaging Height (TDH) and Elutriation models: influence on circulation rate and on air velocity inside the reactor

Once the circulation rate has been calculated, we have to see which is the optimal velocity to grant that circulation happens with the desired rate. If we have fixed the mass flow of air the only way we have to change the velocity to the desired values is to change the section of the reactor. We also know that the average value of the cross section area for both the air and the fuel reactor has been identified to be close to the number of 0.2 m²/MWth [25].

The circulation rate is clearly caused by the elutriation of the particles in the air reactor and is also caused by the fact that the transport disengaging height is higher than the height of the reactor. We will discuss these two technical issues in the following paragraphs.

The equation used to model the elutriation process is the following:

$$k_{i,\infty} = A * \rho_G * u_B * \exp(-C \cdot u_t / u) \quad (8)$$

Where:

- $k_{i,\infty}$ is the elutriation coefficient, expressed in kg/(m²s);
- ρ_G , is the gas density expressed in kg/m³;
- $u_{t,I}$ is the particle terminal velocity, expressed in m/s;
- u is the fluidizing velocity, expressed in m/s.

While the elutriation model refers to the formulation of Tasirin Geldart [26], for the Transport Disengaging Height we consider the model of [27]. In reality there are several empirical models available in the literature to estimate the Transport Disengaging Height (TDH), see for example: [28].

This parameter affects the design of the air reactor in an important way: it is linked with the choice of the height. Generally speaking if we want that a significant quantity of the bed is transported to the cyclone of the air reactor we need to assume that the TDH is higher than the reactor height.

3 Results

3.1 Final design of the air reactor and of the fuel reactor

As already said, the air reactor, which consist of a riser has been modeled with Aspen Plus, V11. This version of the software has already a model to implement a fluidized bed which is available in the section “solids” with the reactor “Fluidbed”. The input parameters used to model the air reactor and the fuel reactor fluidized beds are reported in table 3.

The bed mass is derived directly from the inventory of the air reactor. As already said the diameter and the height of the air reactor are respectively:

- diameter: 1.8 meters
- height: 9.5 meters.

The diameter of the air reactor is selected to grant a velocity which is typical of the fast fluidization regime. The diameter of the fuel reactor is chosen to grant a regime which is close to the bubbling fluidization, in which there is low entrainment and efficient reactions rates.

Dealing with the fuel reactor the dimensions are the following:

- diameter: 3.0 meters;
- height: 6.0 meters.

The detail on the Characteristics of the air reactor and of the circulation riser are described in table 4.

Table 3: Fluidized bed model input parameters

Parameter	Value	Unit of Measure
Voidage at minimum fluidization	0.5	-
Geldart classification	B	-
Minimum fluidization velocity calculation method	Ergun [29]	-
Transport disengagement Height Model	George and Grace [30]	-
Maximum dCv/dh	1e-05	-
Elutriation model	Tasirin & Geldart [31]	-
Decay constant	3	-
TG parameter A1	23.7	-
TG parameter A2	14.5	-
TG parameter B1	2.5	-
TG parameter B2	2.5	-
TG parameter C1	-5.4	-
TG parameter C2	-5.4	-
Constant diameter	-	-
Cross section	circular	-
Solids discharge location	95% of total height	-
Gas distribution	perforated plate	-
Distributor pressure drop	0.04	bar

Table 4: Reactor characteristics are derived from the ASPEN Plus V11 model

Parameter	Air Reactor	Fuel reactor	Unit of Measure
Total reactor height	9.5	6	m
Reactor diameter	1.8	3.0	m
Inventory	10,880	8000	kg
Circulation rate	111	111	Kg/s
Operating pressure	12	12	bar
Height of bottom zone	1.8	0.01	m
Height of freeboard	7.7	5.99	m
Transport Disengaging Height calculated by correlation	18.4	5.33	m
Transport Disengaging Height based on solids volume fraction profile	3.7	3.89	m
Number of particles in bed	1.1E11	3.3E10	-
Surface area	21864	26040	sqm
Minimum fluidization velocity	0.1	0.04	m/sec

As it can be seen from table 4, the inventory and the circulation rate are the values which have been calculated with the help of equations: 2-3 and 8, respectively. The height of the bottom zone is much bigger for the air reactor, not only because it has a higher inventory but also because it has a lower diameter, respect to the air reactor. It is important to note that the air reactor has a transport disengaging height calculated by correlation which is much higher than the total height of the freeboard this is highlighted with a warning by Aspen Plus itself but in the case of the air reactor it is necessary because we want a high intensity of the elutriation process to transport the oxygen carrier to the fuel reactor. In the case of the fuel reactor (where elutriation is not wanted and the oxygen carrier moves by gravity joining the air reactor and passing through the loop seal) the transport disengaging height calculated by correlation is

lower than the total freeboard height and so this allow us to be sure that elutriation is not happening.

3.2 Profiles of velocity, solids volume fraction

The final profiles of:

- superficial velocity (m/s)
- interstitial velocity (m/s)
- solids volume fraction (-)
- Pressure (bar).

The velocities profiles inside the air reactor are proposed in figure 5.

Figure 5: Velocities profiles inside the air reactor

The velocities inside the fuel reactor are proposed in figure 6.

Figure 6: Velocities profiles inside the fuel reactor

As it can be seen from figure 5, the bed of the air reactor is concentrated in the first 1 meter of height of the reactor. This can be seen from the interstitial velocity which is initially higher than the superficial velocity and decreases rapidly when the freeboard begins.

Dealing with the fuel reactor we see in figure 6 that the bed height is still on the same order of magnitude of the air reactor but we will see in the next figures on the solid transport that the solid concentration is completely different because the bed is much concentrated in the bottom zone in the case of the fuel reactor, while in the case of the air reactor the bed results to be

dispersed. The final velocity value of the air reactor results to be about 4 m/s while that of the air reactor is about 0.4 m/s this allows us to say that the two reactors are respectively in the conditions of fast fluidization and bubbling fluidization. The solids volume fraction in the air reactor is presented in figure 7.

Figure 7: Solids volume fraction in the air reactor

Figure 8: Solids volume fraction in the fuel reactor

As said before, in figures 7 and 8 it is shown that the solids distribution inside the air reactor is much more distributed than that in the air reactor. In the air reactor in fact there is the need to entrain the great part of the solids in the flow of air to bring them to the cyclone and then recirculate them. As already explained the Transport Disengaging Height is much more higher than the total freeboard height. On the other hand in the fuel reactor we have a bubbling regime, we want the solids to stay in the bed (which is generally more high but concentrated in the reactor). In the fuel reactor for the above said reasons there is no entrainment. The pressure trend inside the air reactor is shown in figure 9.

Figure 9: Pressure trend in the air reactor

Figure 10: Pressure trend in the fuel reactor

Figures 9 and 10 confirm mainly the data reported in table 4. The air reactor has a bed which is higher respect to that of the fuel reactor due to the higher section of the latter. Nonetheless the bed is dispersed through the whole length of the air reactor ,while in the fuel reactor we have high pressure in the bed zone and the pressure decreases steeply when we enter the freeboard zone.

The decrease in the initial pressure at the inlet of the two reactors obviously represents a pressure loss which can have also a penalty on the whole plat energy efficiency. In figure 11 we evaluate the difference in the pressure loss between the air reactor and the fuel reactor, together with the most important contributions among the different types of pressure losses.

Figure 11: Pressure drop analysis, Air Reactor (AR) – left; Fuel Reactor (FR) - right

As it can be seen from figure 9, in the case of the air reactor, the great contribution to the pressure drop is due to the bed which is inside the air reactor. The contribution of the bed in the fuel reactor is limited because of the increased section; while the contribution of the free board is significant because is much more dense in the case of the fuel reactor itself. The distribution pressure drop due to the injectors that insert air in the air reactor and the fuel in the fuel reactor is very similar. We see from the results shown in figure 11, how important is a careful calculation of the inventory of oxygen carriers in the reactor.

4 Conclusions

The paper has presented a model for the dimensioning of an air reactor and a fuel reactor to be coupled to a gas turbine of the power of about 12 MW, based on the air mass flow requirements to produce such a power. The fluidized beds are designed choosing geometry parameters and making a detailed analysis of the influence of geometry on velocity profiles, solids concentration and pressure drop characteristics. It can be seen from the analysis presented in this paper that the diameter of the fluidized bed is mainly influenced by the mass flow of the air in the reactor, while the height of the reactor is mainly influenced by elutriation and transport disengaging height calculations. Further step will be to couple the air reactor model and the fuel reactor model with two turbo expanders and to introduce more effective models of chemical reactions. Pressure drop in the distributor system and injection orifice optimization can be also more effectively modeled in Aspen Plus and CFD software, performing a sensitivity analysis on the geometrical configuration.

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